

ENGLISH TRANSLATION METHODOLOGY, FAILURES OF ERRORS

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This article addresses some of the common problems that arise in translation studies. It also highlights the current demand for translation studies and its place in society.

Keywords: text, translation, vocabulary, terminology, translation problems, transformation, information.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the rapid development of modern globalization and intercultural relations, the expansion of international relations, the development of trade-economic and financial relations between countries, the strengthening of the process of integration of European countries and the whole world, the development of science and technology, the continuous flow of scientific and technical information Nowadays, the importance of foreign languages as effective factors of organic exchange deserves great attention. Also, at the stage of economic, scientific, technical and cultural development, foreign languages are widely used as a means of oral and written communication between representatives of different peoples of the world.

Due to the rapid development of knowledge and technologies, translators who have practical skills in translating scientific and technical texts related to various fields, covering all aspects in today's society and in the era of changing conditions of the modern economy -specialists are in special demand today. Therefore, the need for highly educated translators is increasing day by day.

Due to the development of modern technologies, today, scientists from different countries of the world have the opportunity to quickly exchange

information and conduct joint research, and thanks to these means of communication, unprecedented results are being achieved in modern science. In such conditions, the need for high-quality translation of scientific literature is significantly increasing in many manufacturing organizations. And translators must constantly add translations of scientific literature to their vocabulary, increase their ability to understand terms and know their meaning.

Therefore, when translating scientific and technical terms, the translator should first of all pay great attention to the meaning from the existing scientific and technical point of view, and then it is necessary to have the ability to compare with narrow scientific and technical terms.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In the process of translation of scientific and technical texts, the following requirements should be followed: translation equivalence, translation accuracy, quality of translation data, logicity of translation and quality of its coverage. In order to have a quality translation of a scientific and technical text, the translator must have the following knowledge and skills:

- Must have knowledge of foreign language theory, phonetics, lexis and grammatical structure of the language;
- Translation of scientific and technical texts to the practice of the skills;
- Linguistic practical knowledge (translation methods, transformation, the ability to replace the equivalent of words, the ability to add words, the ability to describe with terms, etc.);
- In the process of translating the text, it is necessary to have extralinguistic knowledge and the ability to use the content of sentences and sentences (in this case, it was required to have sufficient information in translating a special scientific-technical text).

One of the main unknown problems in translation is that the translator does not have a complete understanding of what "scientific translation" is. In order to

successfully perform a scientific translation, the translator must have an idea of how it differs from other types of translation. In general, the translation of the scientific method includes many texts related to the research topic - from theses, includes abstracts and article reviews, diplomas, dissertations and monograph manuscripts.

When translating the above types of work, attention should be paid to the following factors: the purpose of translation, the method of translation, the organization of the text in the translation and the relationship between its parts.

In addition to the external structure of academic texts (chapters, sections, paragraphs), there is also an internal structure. The translation of scientific texts has its own characteristics - it is a method of defining material problems from general information and presenting their solution. For example, English has a number of words and phrases that are used for different purposes, to connect parts of text together, as well as to change the meaning of one phrase to another. For example:

- also (in addition, furthermore, furthermore...);
- in spite of (although, however, despite, in spite of, nevertheless...);
- in other words (in other words);
- for example (for example, for instance...).

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Terminology problems in translation.

It is one of the leading forms of scientific thinking and it is related to the concepts of understanding and perception of meaning. Almost every term in a scientific text is a lexical unit, and it expresses one of the meanings of special lexical units. These lexical units belong to the category of terms.

In general, a term is a word or phrase that is specific to a certain field in the field of science and technology. The term has clear semantic boundaries in linguistics. It follows that terms are a system of concepts reinforced by verbal expressions related to a particular discipline. If a word in common language (except for a term) has many meanings, but it falls into the category of terms, then this word

will have a specific meaning, and its meaning in the term will be used in the translation.

Therefore, one of the main mistakes that a translator makes when translating a scientific text is that he does not have enough skills to use scientific dictionaries or does not have a clear knowledge of the subject specific to the term - this situation is even his own. can also be observed in the mother tongue. In terms of usage and quantity, specialized vocabularies of terms are more widely used in scientific method texts than other types of vocabularies. They are: nomenclature names, professional vocabulary and terms, professional jargon, etc. This lexicon is widely used in all areas of scientific text (that is, text classification, text structure and its function, text components and factors are also taken into account). On average, terminological or terminological vocabulary makes up 20% of the total vocabulary of scientific texts.

Grammatical problems in translation.

The style of scientific communication has its own grammatical features. For example, when some texts are translated from English to Uzbek, in some cases the lexical meaning is lost and the verbs have an abstract meaning. For example:

- It seems very interesting - Bu juda qiziq ko'rinadi.
- He probably got a cold - Balki u shamollab qolgan.
- Ali feels himself strange - Ali o'zini g'alati his qilayapti.

In these cases, we can see that the semantic load falls on verbs instead of noun phrases. In other words, verbs perform an important grammatical function in these sentences.

Also, abstract verbs are often used in scientific method texts in English:

- Many houses were built in short term - Ko'pgina uylar qisqa mudatda qurilgan;
- Some new planets were discovered in mid of 2000's - 2000-yillarda bir qancha yangi sayyoralar kashf qilingan (topilgan).

As can be seen in the above examples, abstract nouns are also widely used in English, and the main focus is on verbs, that is, on passive participles.

Another interesting aspect of the study is that in today's linguistics, the percentage of use of present tense verbs in English is equal to that of past tense verbs, which of course depends on the context of the scientific text.

In general, a scientific text must have a clear statement of logic, and translating this logic into a correct and high-quality translation is one of the most important tasks of a translator. Texts in the scientific style, in most cases, have a homogeneous appearance, but these texts have expressive features. In such texts, interrogative sentences are rarely used, even if they are used, they are directed to draw the attention of the reader who is familiar with the text. One of the characteristics of scientific texts is that emotional expressions are not used.

General theory of translation.

The general theory of translation systematizes the conclusions derived from the concrete experience of translation and creates a basis for it. In the process of translation, of translation its results and ideas are summarized, and the conditions and factors specific to translation are taken into account in the translation activity. The concept of the general theory of translation was developed by the Russian linguist and linguist A.V. Widely and fully covered in the works of Fedorov. According to this concept, any quality translation text should begin with a philological analysis of its linguistic basis and end with an artistic creation or scientific editing.

A special theory of translation.

A special theory of translation (or research on translation focused on a pair in linguistics) should take into account the equivalents, variants of the correspondence between two languages, as well as the factors and criteria for their selection in a specific situation. The main method of studying translation phenomena within this

theory is the comparison of two languages. For example: Uzbek and Russian, or Russian and English, or English and German.

Transformational theory of translation

The transformational theory (model) of translation is represented by making changes to the translated text during the translation activity. The reason is that in some cases the meaning of the text cannot be fully translated or it is difficult to translate.

CONCLUSION

For example:

Not long-ago computers were considered an amazing invention. Today they form part of our everyday lives. The latest thing today is Virtual Reality. A Virtual Reality system can transport the user to exotic locations such as a beach in Hawaii or the inside of the human body.

Uzbek language translation:

O'tgan davrda kompyuterlar ajoyib ixtiro deb hisoblanar edi. Bugungi kunda ular bizning kundalik hayotimizning bir qismini tashkil qiladi. Oxirgi ixtrolardan biri - bu Virtual haqiqat. Virtual haqiqat tizimi foydalanuvchlarni Gavayidagi plyaj yoki inson tanasining ichki qismi kabi ekzotik joylarga olib borish imkoniyatiga ega.

As we can see in the example, the translation from English to Uzbek was not completely translated, but instead underwent a transformation. That is, the meaning of the original text in the Uzbek language is clarified with other words.

The transformational model of translation is related to the ideas of American linguist N. Chomsky "transformational or generative grammar". Within this theory, the process of creating a translation text is considered as a syntactic transformation of the units and structures of the source language into the units and structures of the translated language, with great attention being paid to the stages and methods of the translation process. Also, this theory is supported by American translators K. Naide, B.O. It is also mentioned in the works of Kads and W. Koller. In general, the ideas

of transformational theory are one of the important methods that allow translation studies to identify structures and units that are related to translation and interrelated in the process of translating a pair of languages.

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